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Conference Abstract

MAWDŪDĪ'S RESPONSE TO MODERN SCIENCE: A POSITION BETWEEN THE EXTREMES

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ABSTRACT

This paper examines Maududi's response to modern science, exploring his position as a middle ground between uncritical acceptance and outright rejection. Maududi acknowledged the potential benefits of modern science while emphasizing the Islamization of modern scientific practices and procedures. Similarly, he also accepted the significance of Islamic tradition as it holds a valuable aspect. However, Maududi neither unconditionally accepts Islamic tradition and scientific practices and procedures nor rejects them outright, instead advocating a balanced approach that selectively integrates both tradition and modern science with Islamic teachings. This paper explores Maudūdī's position by highlighting his approach to Islamizing modern science. It employs an analytical research methodology with a qualitative approach. It prioritizes primary sources but also uses secondary sources when needed.

Keywords: Islamic tradition, Modern science, Islamization, Modernity, Islamic science

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